

SUSTAINABLE SCIENCE RESEARCH

APPLICATION OF HELIGMAN AND POLLARD MODEL AND SMOOTH SPLINE POISON REGRESSION TO MODELING FEMALE MORTALITY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Child Mortality modeling has dominated the centre stage of Statistical Modeling. Little effort has been geared towards developing a mortality model that captured Nigeria general mortality rate. This research paper, focus on the Female Mortality Modeling using Heligman and Pollard Mortality model with Spline Smooth Poison Regression Model. We considered the robustness of the two models as they both fit into the Nigeria Female mortality data for 2002 to 2006. The Heligman and Pollard model fit the data very well but there is no Basic rule of estimating the parametes. Spline Smooth Poison Regression Model with the smoothing parameter to be 0.00316, with AIC to be 268.88 and BIC as 274.21 having effective dimension as 5.992.

INTRODUCTION

Indicators obtained from mortality rates provide a good picture of overall population health. These indicators include infant and child mortality, adult mortality and overall life expectancy at birth. According to the world development indicators database, adult mortality rate" is the probability of a fifteen year old dying before reaching age sixty, if subjected to current age-specific mortality rates between those ages.

For several decades, global public-health efforts have focused on the development and application of disease control programs to improve child survival in developing countries. Consequently, methods for calculating child mortality levels and trends from surveys are well-developed and generally yield accurate estimates. By contrast, little emphasis has been placed on adult mortality especially in a developing country like Nigeria. Although attempts have been made to measure adult mortality, these attempts have often produced implausibly low estimates of adult mortality. As a result, many are remarkably ignorant about current level and patterns of adult mortality in the country, and how they are changing with time.

In September 2000, all the 191 United Nations member states pledged that by the year 2015, all the MDGs consisting of a frame of 8 goals, 18 targets and 48 indicators to track progress towards meeting the goals would be met. Goal 5 focuses on issues relating to maternal mortality and maternal health. The target is to reduce by three-quarters, between 1990 and 2015, the maternal mortality ratio. Goal 6 is aimed at targets in epidemiology of HIV/AIDS, malaria and other major diseases leading to adult mortality and their social consequences. It is expected that these diseases must have halted and their spread reversed by 2020. This is year 2013 the question is; will Nigeria be able to meet up with these goals?

The Government needs accurate information on deaths in the population to help them plan health care policies and monitor the effectiveness of public-health programs designed in order to achieve the MDG targets. Without details on adult mortality, it is hard to identify effective strategies for curbing adult mortality in the country.

Modeling is one of the MDGs indicators. According to Bamiduro (2007), a good model is measurable, tractable, efficient and identifiable. It must allow for the application of all the three functions of statistics namely description, inference and prescription providing insight where necessary into the development and

implication of the events being measured. These reasons underline the choice of developing a statistical model that fit Nigeria data.

Data: The source of the data for this research work is from Nigeria Federal bureau of Statistics data jointly obtained by the Bureau and Central Bank of Nigeria on mortality by age and gender from 2002 to 2006. For the purpose of this research work, we have used the provided data.

Mortality Model

The development of a law of mortality, in which an analytic expression is used to represent all or part of the age pattern of mortality (in term of, say $\mu(x)$ or $q(x)$), has been of interest since the development of the first life table, which is compiled by renowned English astronomer Edmund Hellely (1693). Probably, the first mathematical mortality model is the one proposed by Abraham De Moivre's in 1725, who suggested that the probability of survival from birth until age x could be expressed as linear function of age. In terms of the hazard rate, the model can be written as:

$$\mu(x) = \frac{1}{\omega - x}, 0 \leq x \leq \omega \quad (1)$$

where ω is the highest attainable age.

However, the most successful and influential mortality law belongs to Benjamin Gompertz. In 1825, Gompertz found that an exponential increase in age can approximately capture the behavior of human mortality rates for large portions of the life table. He therefore proposed, in terms of the hazard rate, that:

$$\mu(x) = A \exp(\theta x), x > 0 \quad (2)$$

The Gompertz law has played a central role in the development of theoretical hypotheses about the pattern of mortality. The close fit of the Gompertz function to empirical data seems to suggest that a law of mortality may exist to explain the age patterns of death for human populations. This has stimulated a lot of researches to modify or generalize the Gompertz formula.

For example, in 1860, William Makeham noticed that the Gompertz equation failed to capture the behavior of mortality at higher ages and added a constant term, B , in order to correct for this deficiency. The constant can be thought of representing the risk of death by causes that are independent of age. Hence Makeham's model can be expressed as

$$\mu(x) = B + A \exp(\theta x) \quad (3)$$

Another good extension from Gompertz's model is Perks's model (1932),

$$\mu(x) = \frac{B + A \exp(\theta x)}{1 + C \exp(\theta x)} \quad (4)$$

which allows the curve to more closely approximate the slower rate of increase in mortality at older ages.

Also in 1963, Beard developed a model to reflect the effect of heterogeneity in the mortality risks to alter the shape of the mortality rate increasing:

$$\mu(x) = \frac{A \exp(\theta x)}{1 + C \exp(\theta x)} \quad (5)$$

In 1980, Heligman and Pollard extended Gompertz's law to an eight parameter formula that can better fit the whole mortality curve, models. A well known graduation technique is the use of a mathematical formula,

$$\frac{q_x}{1 - q_x} = A(x + B)^C + D \exp\left(-E \left(\log\left(\frac{x}{F}\right)\right)^2\right) + GH^x$$

(6)

The model:

Heligman and pollard (1980) proposed the above model, which describes the entire life time. They applied the model to fit the Australian life table. The three components of the formula represent early childhood mortality, accident mortality and senescent mortality respectively. The third component GH^x is interpreted as a discrete version of the Gompertz law where q_x is the probability that a person at age $x+1$, $px = 1 - qx$ and A to H are parameters. When applying the model, the parameters are determined by minimizing the square sum of

$$s^2 = \sum_{x=0}^x \left(\frac{q_x}{\mu_x} - 1 \right)^2$$

(7)

Where, q_x represents the fitted mortality and μ_x represents the observed mortality.

We analyze our data instead of age $x+1$ as used by Heligman and pollard in their original work by using age $x+5$. The model is used for the analysis as shown below.

PENALIZED LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION

Penalized likelihood estimation is a likelihood based estimation method which traces its origin back to Whittaker (1923) (discrete case) and Kimeldorf and Wahba(1970a,70b,71)and Good and Gaskins (1971). The central idea is to estimate a function of interest on

$$L(\eta | data) + \frac{\lambda}{2} J(\eta)$$

(8)

Where $L(\eta|data)$ is the negative log-likelihood and $J(\eta)$ is a quadratic roughness penalty with a low dimensional null-space $NJ = \{ f \in H : J(f) = 0 \}$. The minimizer above can be seen to be the restricted maximum likelihood estimator in a model space $M_{\rho} = \{ f : J(f) = \rho \}$ for some $\rho > 0$. Moreover, λ above can be seen to be the Lagrange Multiplier.

An example of the above formulation is the cubic smoothing spline, see Klugman, Panjerand Willmott (2004). It arises from the regression problem

$$Y_i = \eta(x_i) + e_i, i = 1, \dots, n$$

(9)

Where e_i are independent random variables with $e_i \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$. Let us assume that $[0, 1]$, $i = 1, \dots, n$. Then with the quadratic roughness penalty taken to be $\int_0^1 \ddot{\eta}(x)^2 dx$ where $\ddot{\eta}$ is the second derivative of η Now (9) in this problem is equivalent to

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \left(\frac{y_i - \eta(x)}{\delta_i} \right)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{2} \int_0^1 \hat{\eta}(x)^2 dx$$

(10)

and from elementary properties of spline we see that the minimizer has to be a cubic spline which is called the cubic smoothing spline. The above setup naturally leads to functional spaces which are Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces (RKHS) as the optimization problem then becomes tractable. This is so as the log likelihood, being a smooth function of the evaluation functionals, and be a continuous functional requires that the function space (a Hilbert space) to be a RKHS. Moreover, it is then natural to take the smoothness

penalty J to be one induced by a semi-inner product on the RKHS. This general setup is useful in extending the method to multivariate function estimation and allows one to consider interesting classes of smooth functions, see Gu (2002). Of particular interest is the equivalence of the penalized likelihood method to a Bayes model with a Gaussian prior on $H\Theta$ NJ (with the covariance related to the reproducing kernel) and a diffuse prior on NJ . This Bayes model makes available Bayesian posterior confidence intervals. And these become approximate Bayesian confidence intervals in the case of non-Gaussian response as it involves quadratic approximation of the likelihood (Laplace’s method).

Smoothing parameter selection is an important practical issue in penalized likelihood estimation. There are different score based methods, the scores being asymptotically close to

$$\frac{1}{n} = \sum_{i=0}^n n\lambda((x_i) - \eta(x_i))^2 \tag{11}$$

The idea being that the smoothing parameter is chosen to minimize the above. For details see Gu (2002). Interestingly, using the generalized cross validation based score for choosing the smoothing parameter results in the point wise Bayesian confidence intervals having good across-the-function coverage, see Gu (2002) and references there in for more details.

Let Dx , for $x = 0, 1, \dots$, be the number of deaths observed at age (according to any of the common used definition) x . Also let E_x , for $x = 0, 1, \dots$, be the total amount of time the persons were under observation at age x . We assume that Dx is a Poisson distributed random variable with parameter $E_x \lambda(x)$, i.e.

$$\Pr(Dx = k) = \frac{1}{k!} \lambda(x) E(x)^k \exp(-E_x \lambda(x)) \sum_{x=0}^x \left(\frac{qx}{\mu x} - 1 \right)^2 \tag{12}$$

Such a Poisson distribution has been assumed by many, for e.g. see Forfar, McCutcheon and Wilkie (1988). Assuming the constant force of mortality within integral ages results in the same likelihood as the above Poisson likelihood, see Hoem (1984). This fact has been used in the Bayesian analysis of Broffitt (1988). Also for an argument that the Poisson distribution assumption results from using the above constant force assumption, see Scott (1982, 1984). In this connection also interesting are the articles Sverdup (1965) and Borgan (1984). In the following we will assume the constant force within integral ages.

Given the above model we suppose that $\eta(\cdot) = \log \lambda(\cdot)$ lies in the space of all twice continuously differentiable functions and by using the roughness penalty

$$\int \ddot{\eta}(x)^2 dx \tag{13}$$

where $\ddot{\eta}$ is the second derivative of η

we force the estimate to be a cubic spline. Estimates for qx are derived using the formula

$$q_x = 1 - \exp[-\lambda(x)] \tag{14}$$

which result from the constant force assumption.

The choice of selecting smoothing parameter

The user of P -splines has a number of choices to make: (a) the number of knots, the degree of the P -spline and the order of the penalty, and (b) the smoothing parameter. The parameters in (a) we call the P -spline parameters and denote them by ndx , $bdeg$ and $pord$ respectively. We will see that when forecasting with P -splines the forecast values depend critically on the order of the penalty. The choice of the other P -spline parameters, ndx and $bdeg$, can be less critical since different choices often lead to similar fitted smooth functions. Eilers and Marx (1996), Ruppert (2002) and Currie and Durban (2002) discuss the choice of the

P-spline parameters; the following simple rule-of-thumb is often sufficient: We will use the Bayesian Information Criterion, BIC and Aike information criterion to choose the smoothing parameter

$$AIC(R, \lambda) = n \log(RSS(R, \lambda)) + 2df(R, \lambda) \tag{15}$$

where

$$RSS(R, \lambda) = \{y - \mu_\lambda(x)\}^T R^{-1} \{y - \mu_\lambda(x)\}$$

and

$$df(R, \lambda) = \text{tr}(S_R, \lambda), \text{ with } \text{tr}(\cdot) \text{ as trace of the matrix.}$$

$$BIC = 2Dev + \log n Tr$$

Where

Dev is the deviance in a generalized Linear Model (GLM)

and $Tr = \text{tr}(H)$ is the effective dimension of the fitted model and n is the number of observation.

AIC and BIC have been used for this work, but there is evidence that BIC performed better than AIC which is believed to be under-smooth the data. See for example, Hurvich et al. (1998) or Lee (2003). BIC penalizes model complexity heavily than AIC.

Application and Discussion of the Result

We analyze the data using both solver technique in excel and gss from R package as shown below.

Figure1:

The parameter for Heligman and Pollard Model for 2002-2006 are shown below

Figure2: Helingman and pollard eight parameter

Year/parameter	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006
A	0.06	0.05	0.09	0.05	0.08
B	0.02	0.04	0.24	0.08	0.05
C	0.08	0.08	0.34	0.03	0.98
D	0.05	0.01	0.07	0.06	0.8
E	12	24	23	28	32
F	0.05	0.88	0.01	0.7	0.88
G	0.8	0.02	0.09	0.90	0.6
H	0.06	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.06
Error	12.4112	13.77264	16.7719	11.013	7.2834

Figure 2: Helingman and Pollard eight parameter

Figure 3: Log Mortality for Female in Nigeria

DISCUSSION

From the analysis, we discovered that Heligman and Pollard mortality curve of series three which is 2004 mortality curve of figure 1 slope down gently and portrait the picture that the mortality for each age group is high throughout that period. The other years curve slope down sharply as one move from childhood age to youthful age and rise sharply as the ages are above seventy. The parameters and the errors for the Heligman

and Pollard Model were given in figure 2 and the graph showing the eight parameters for those years under study is in figure

3. The problem with this model is that starting with different values may lead to having different parameters. As good as the model fits the data very well; there is no basic solution to arrive at the best parameters.

Based on the deficiency of the earlier model we analyze our data using the proposed model smoothing spline poisson regression. From the analysis the following results were obtained and displayed in figure 3 and four respectively.

Effective dimension = 17.83 and the (Selected) smoothing parameter = 0.00316

The Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) = 274.21, and Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) = 268.88

(Estimated) dispersion parameter (ψ^2) = 21.4 and the convergence tolerance of the model is 4.5382-08.

The AIC and BIC allowed for the selection of the best smoothing parameter.

The model show a smooth rise in the log-mortality as Age increases except some situations we have a sharp rise and fall as portrait by the curve of figure 3

Further research area using this model is the computation of life table and forecast for future mortality.

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